

A 50-100 GHz ohmic contact SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch with dual axis movement

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Abstract

We firstly show the prototype of an ohmic contact Single-Pole Double-Throw Radio Frequency Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (SPDT RF MEMS) switch operating at 50-100 GHz. The fabricated ohmic contact SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch moves both laterally and vertically, to improve the isolation at high frequencies by initially misaligning the contact part of the switch over a Coplanar Waveguide (CPW) transmission line. The lateral and vertical movement of the switch is operated by using comb and parallel plate actuators, respectively. The proposed switch was fabricated using Silicon-On-Glass (SiOG) bonding process. The insertion loss of the fabricated switch is measured according to the different operation states of the switch, in the range from 50 to 100 GHz. The fabricated length of the transmission line is 4.6 mm and the measured insertion loss and isolation are 9.13 dB and 24.37 dB at 70 GHz, respectively.

Keyword

RF MEMS switch; high isolation; dual axis movement; silicon switch

1. Introduction

A microwave system broadly utilizes SPDT switches for radio frequency applications, the SPDT switches are used for selecting between swapping inputs, two power sources, or any device with two ports flowing into or from one common port.

Microwave switches are fabricated using semiconductor-based PIN diode and FET. According to advances in photolithography and integration technology, microwave switches can be fabricated using MEMS processes. A RF MEMS switch has a number of advantages such as a wide bandwidth, high isolation, low insertion loss, low power consumption, and small size. RF MEMS switches are recently being used in many applications. Thus, the conventional semiconductor switches are being replaced by RF switches using MEMS technology [1-3].

The RF MEMS switch can be mainly classified as an ohmic contact RF MEMS switch or a capacitive shunt RF MEMS switch according to operating methods. The ohmic contact RF MEMS switch can operate from DC to tens of GHz. On the other hand, the capacitive RF MEMS switch has a frequency range over a few GHz, because the switch is operated by capacitance variation. Generally, in terms of structure simplicity, charging problem, compatibility with a microstrip line, robustness, and reliability, the ohmic contact RF MEMS switch performs better than the capacitive RF MEMS switch for frequencies less than 50 GHz [4-6]. In this paper, by using dual axis movement the SPDT ohmic contact switch is used up to 100 GHz.

Conventionally the ohmic contact RF MEMS switches are operated by contact part movement along only one axis (horizontal or vertical direction) [7-9]. Because the switch is single axis operated, the contact part of the switch is usually positioned directly over the opened signal line in the OFF-state. Thus, a typical ohmic contact RF MEMS switch operated at high frequencies generates an unwanted coupling capacitance between the contact part and the opened signal line, which worsens the isolation characteristics of the switch. In order to minimize the coupling capacitance and increase the isolation, the ohmic contact SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch is fabricated with dual axis movement (horizontal and vertical direction). The advantage of using dual axis movement is to reduce the initial

coupling capacitance which determines the isolation of the ohmic contact RF MEMS silicon switch in the OFF-state. Namely, the contact parts of the proposed switch are misaligned in the OFF-state to reduce the initial coupling capacitance, which is the main difference compared to typical ohmic contact RF MEMS switches [10-12]. The concept and simple verification of a SPST switch for high isolation through two directional motions has been described in [10, 11]. In this paper a three port SPDT switch is designed, fabricated and measured at high frequencies. The SPDT switch has been initially designed to misalign the two contact parts in opposite directions from CPW line, the design allows moving one contact part at a time over the CPW line, at that time, the other contact part of the switch will be misaligned for high isolation. This design can route the signal flowing from the common port through one of two possible outputs, while providing a high isolation at the other port. Preliminary results were reported in [12], this paper includes detailed design, fabrication and results.

In this paper, the ohmic contact SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch with advanced RF characteristics within the frequency range from 50 to 100 GHz is designed and fabricated using a parallel plate actuator and a comb actuator for dual axis movement. RF characteristics of the fabricated ohmic contact RF MEMS silicon switch is measured with respect to the different operation states of the switch.

2. DESIGN

Fig. 1 shows the schematic view of the ohmic contact SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch, which consists of two actuators for dual axis movement and two contact parts. The contact parts of the switches are distantly situated away from the opened signal line to improve the isolation characteristic in the OFF-state (Fig. 2(a)). To operate separately the two switches by using bidirectional actuation by means of the comb actuator, switches A and B are laterally misaligned by 30 μm towards the positive and negative y-direction respectively. The proposed RF MEMS switch is operated according to the following procedure to produce the ON-state. First, the switch is laterally moved by the comb actuator which is actuated by the electrostatic force between the comb electrodes (Fig. 2(b) and (c)). If the switches are moved 30 μm along the positive y-direction (lateral movement), the contact part of switch A is laterally positioned over the opened signal line. At this time, the lateral

distance between the contact part of switch B and the opened signal line is 60 μm . If the switches are moved 30 μm along the negative y-direction, the contact part of switch B is correctly positioned over the opened signal line. After the contact part of the desired switch A or B is correctly positioned over the opened transmission line, the corresponding contact part is vertically moved 2.5 μm along the negative z-direction (vertical movement) by the electrostatic force between an upper electrode and a bottom electrode (Fig. 2(d)). Finally, the desired switch A or B is turned on when the opened signal line is connected through the switch contact part, following the procedure described above.

The CPW line, which has an input port and two output ports is used for the SPDT system. The designed gap and width of the CPW line is 10 μm and 70 μm , respectively, the impedance of the CPW line is matched to 50 Ω according to the dimensions of the CPW line. Table 1 shows the geometrical parameters of the comb actuator. The force (F) acting on the comb actuator movable mass is expressed as follows,

$$F = \frac{\varepsilon_0 N_{\text{comb}} h}{d_{\text{comb}}} V_{\text{lateral}}^2 - k_f x. \quad (1)$$

When the electrostatic force equals (F=0), (1) is expressed as follows,

$$k_f x = \frac{\varepsilon_0 N_{\text{comb}} h}{d_{\text{comb}}} V_{\text{lateral}}^2, \quad (2)$$

then, V_{lateral} can be derived from (2),

$$V_{\text{lateral}} = \sqrt{\frac{k_f x d_{\text{comb}}}{\varepsilon_0 N_{\text{comb}} h}}, \quad (3)$$

where ε_0 is the vacuum permittivity, N_{comb} is the number of comb electrodes, h is the height of the comb electrode, d_{comb} is the gap between comb electrodes, k_f is the spring constant along the y-direction, and x is the switch traveled distance.

Based on the dimensions of the designed comb actuator, Fig.3 shows V_{comb} calculated according to the traveled distance. In order to laterally align the contact part of the switch with the opened signal line, a potential of 60.29 V should be applied at the comb actuator.

Table 2 shows the geometrical parameters of the parallel plate actuator. A vertical actuation voltage between the upper electrode and bottom electrode is expressed as follows [13],

$$V_{\text{vertical}} = \sqrt{\frac{8k_c g^3}{27\epsilon_0 A}}, \quad (4)$$

where k_c is the spring constant of the double crab leg spring, g is the distance of the gap between the contact part and the open signal line, A is the electrode area, and V_{vertical} is the vertical actuation voltage. Fig. 4 shows the calculated vertical actuation voltage according to the gap. In order to connect the opened signal line, a potential of more than 14.86 V is required as the vertical actuation voltage.

3. FABRICATION

A high-resistivity silicon wafer and a Pyrex 7740 glass wafer are the two substrates used for the fabrication of the RF MEMS switch. First, 4 μm -deep trenches are etched on the silicon wafer via the Deep Reactive-Ion Etching (DRIE) process (Fig. 5(a)). Then 500 nm-thick aluminum layers are patterned to prevent footing effects during the DRIE process (Fig. 5(b)). 500 nm-thick silicon dioxide layers and gold layers which are used as the contact parts of the switches are sequentially patterned (Fig. 5(c)). 500 nm-thick gold layers are patterned to define the CPW line on the glass wafer (Fig. 5(d)), the bottom electrode is patterned for vertical actuation (Fig. 5(d)). The prepared two wafers are anodically bonded as shown in Fig. 5(e) (temperature of 380 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and potential of 800 V) [14]. The silicon wafer thickness is reduced to 50 μm using Chemical Mechanical Polishing (CMP) as shown in Fig. 5(f). The thermally evaporated aluminum layers used as etch mask for the DRIE process are patterned by using lift-off process (Fig. 5(g)). Finally, until the switch structure is released, the DRIE process is followed, after releasing the structure, the aluminum layers are removed (Fig. 5(h) and 5(i)). Fig. 6 shows SEM images of the fabricated switch, CPW lines, comb actuator and contact parts. An air bridge on the CPW line is then inserted to provide equal ground potential, removing signal distortion.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

RF characteristics of the proposed ohmic contact SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch are measured at the three different states of switch operation, the switch is operated by

sequential movement to obtain high isolation in the OFF-state. The lateral and vertical actuation voltage is not applied at the first step (OFF-state). In the second step, a lateral actuation voltage of 60 V is applied to produce the lateral movement of the contact parts. In the third step, the applied vertical actuation voltage (60 V) was higher than the designed voltage (15 V). In practice, the surface of the fabricated contact layers present surface roughness and the size of the contact area were too small, these two facts led to an increase in the vertical actuation voltage. The surface roughness and size of the contact area directly affected the contact resistance, which is determined by the current flow at the contact part. Thus, a low contact resistance is required to improve the RF characteristics of the switch in the ON-state [15]. 60 V was applied as the vertical actuation voltage in order to decrease the contact resistance using a high contact force, caused by using a high vertical actuation voltage.

The RF characteristic of the fabricated ohmic contact SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch was measured using a network analyzer in the frequency range from 50 GHz to 100 GHz. Fig. 7 describes the measured insertion loss and isolations for every state of operation of the switch. The switch measured isolation is improved in the range from 50 GHz to 100 GHz compared to conventional switch design. The initial OFF state produces an isolation of -22.44 dB, this isolation decreased to -17.91 dB after lateral movement of the contact part (this state corresponds to conventional switch design, where the contact part is placed on top of the CPW line). The designed switch with its initially misaligned contact part improves the isolation at high frequencies. Two directional motions allow operating the switch, where the lateral motion is used to improve the switch isolation and the vertical movement is used to produce the ON state of the switch, after the contact part is aligned over the CPW line. We expected that the main performance degradation reason is due to the damaged CPW ground produced during the anodic bonding process, which leads to an impedance mismatched transmission line. Fig. 8 shows the damaged ground of the CPW line, which lead to impedance mismatching of the CPW line. It is considered that the Cr layer adhesion force between the Au layer and glass substrate would be decreased by the oxidization of the Cr layer during the anodic bonding process. The damage of the CPW ground, caused by bonding can be prevented by annealing the glass substrate before the anodic bonding process [16].

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented the prototype of an ohmic contact SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch with dual axis movement using both comb and parallel plate actuators. The ohmic contact switch isolation in the OFF state at high frequencies is improved by using a sequential movement of the switch contact parts, achieved by using two actuators. The initially misaligned contact part over the CPW line produces the high isolation by minimizing the OFF-state capacitance of the switch. This paper demonstrates an SPDT switch that can misalign one contact while having the other one aligned and vice versa. The design can be used to produce high isolation SPDT switches at high frequencies by using two axis movements and the configuration described in this paper. However, the overall measurement results were not excellent due to the impedance mismatch of the CPW line, owing to design and fabrication issues. We expect the performance will be improved by an optimized design and fabrication.

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Tables

Table 1. Geometrical parameters of the comb actuator

h	d_{comb}	N_{comb}	ε₀	k_f
50 μm	5 μm	165	8.85 × 10 ⁻¹² F/m	1.769 N/m

Table 2. Geometrical parameters of the parallel plate actuator

k_c	g	A
50 μm	2.5 μm	2.89 × 10 ⁻⁸ m ²

Figure Captions

Fig. 1. Schematic view of the SPDT MEMS silicon switch

Fig. 2. SPDT MEMS silicon switch actuation procedure (a) top view of switch A and B in

the OFF-state, (b) overview of laterally aligned switch A, (c) overview of switch A making contact

Fig. 3. Actuation voltage vs distance for the lateral actuator

Fig. 4. Actuation voltage vs distance for the vertical actuator

Fig. 5. Fabrication process of the SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch

Fig. 6. (a) SEM images of the fabricated SPDT switch, (b) parallel plate actuator, (c) comb actuator

Fig. 7. Measured insertion loss (only switch A is operated)

Fig. 8. SEM images of the damaged CPW line

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Fig. 5 Fabrication process of SPDT RF MEMS silicon switch

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6. (a) SEM images of fabricated SPDT switch, (b) parallel plate actuator, (c) comb actuator

Fig. 7. Measured insertion loss (only switch A is actuated)

Fig. 8. SEM images of damaged CPW line